

SPIRITUAL AND ETHICAL VIEWS OF FARIDIDDIN ATTOR AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH THINKING

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Abstract: In this article discusses the spiritual and moral views and concepts of Farididdin Attar. Also, the theoretical foundations of the influence of F. Attar's views on the development of the thinking of young people are substantiated.

Key words: Education and training, spirituality, philosophy, mysticism, scientific heritage, educational system.

Introduction.

Attar's worldview is based on the teachings of Sufism, which is an advanced stream of medieval Eastern Islamic philosophy. Sufism is a complex and fascinating philosophical movement with its own ideological foundations. Attar is one of the great figures of Sufism. Therefore, researching Attar's worldview is an arduous process that requires great mental strength, high intelligence and taste, careful observation, and delicate analysis. Many works can be written about Attar's worldview. Attar's spiritual world can be assumed to be such a big ocean that the deeper one dives into it, the more valuable and the more jewels one can find. Unfortunately, I hope that the dear readers of Kamina, who felt far from the path and ambition of diving into such a great ocean, will accept it as a drop from this ocean. Attar's works, whether they are based on direct philosophical considerations or works with symbolic predictions, serve first of all to illuminate the writer's worldview. His creative way is the way to discover divine secrets. In this way, Attar is not a poet-philosopher, but a philosopher. Davlatshah Samarkandi, a historian of the 15th century, emphasized this point and wrote that "*poetry was not his profession or habit.*" So, in all of Attar's works, the philosophical-mystical worldview is in the main place¹.

Attar's work "Mantiq-ut-Tair" is a complex epic full of multi-layered philosophical, spiritual-ethical and social ideas with a dark symbolic tone. Its main theme is devoted to the issue of the relationship between man and the divine. It consists of a main leading story and a parable that serves to prove the main idea of the main theme of the work, as well as small stories. In the epic "*Mantik-ut-Tair*" all the birds gather together and hold a meeting. However, conflicts arise in matters of order at the party, i.e., place - rank, respect, honor, authority, greatness - inferiority, humility and arrogance, self-knowledge and ignorance. Birds feel that it is necessary to elect an honest, just and truthful king, and thus to put an end to the quarrels and conflicts that have occurred in their community. At the same time, Popushak Hudhud prophesied and said that there is a king Semurgh from the bird race, who knows the situation of birds inside and out, and although he is very close to birds, the birds have become far away from him due to their carelessness and ignorance. Now the birds say that they can get rid of

¹ Z.B.Jalilov. Sharq mutafakkirlari merosini o'rganishning didaktik metodlari. Zamonaviy ta'lim jurnali. 2017 yil, 5-son.

all dangers and conflicts if they are attracted to this Semurg's visage. The birds are happy and offer to take Hudhud to this Semurg dargah. Hudhud also describes the prospect of many arduous difficulties and painful trials that Semurg will inevitably face in the process of reaching his destination. It is known that Attar expresses his idea of tariqat here through the image of Hudhud and birds. That is, it is translated into the language of verse as a symbolic advice of a mentor to people who have lost their minds and become heedless through Hudhud.

Tariqat is an Arabic word that means a path, a leech. As for the meaning of the words "*Leech*" and "*Murid*", it usually refers to the goal of a student who steps on the path of Sufism, purifying himself from spiritual, physical and moral aspects, striving for perfection, divine. They are students and students who are studying on the way to attaining enlightenment and attaining the truth, that is, the wealth of the noble soul. Some scholars divide the leech into three parts, consisting of shari'a, tariqat, and truth. Those who hold the first type of view consider enlightenment as a component of reality and separate it from the series of stages. According to those of the third type of view, the Sharia is the rules that every Muslim must follow, and since the main criteria of the Sharia are reflected in the tariqat, it is not mentioned separately in many cases, but starts from the stage of the tariqat.

According to the researches, Sufism teachers defined tariqa as "*true, right path*". It was specially emphasized that the people of the Tariqat should be an example to others in three things, i.e. posture, step, and grace. In this case, it is necessary to refrain from inappropriate words, to refrain from doing things in vain, to do useful things with kindness, to be open-faced and kind. Every murid who has entered the path of the Tariqat must renounce the worldly life, the troubles of the soul, lust, physical pleasures, arrogance, dry fame, heedlessness and ignorance, and purify his spiritual world, all his will and thoughts he had to concentrate his imagination in one place and direct it towards a noble goal.

In the path of religion, there is always a conflict between faith and ignorance, will and hesitation, perseverance and regret, love and hatred. On this path, only those who have true faith, strong will, and endure various sufferings can achieve a high status. Accordingly, even in "*Mantik-ut-Tair*" the birds were attached to the fire of divine love of Semurg and happily set foot on this path, but some of the birds could not withstand the conflicting tests. They apologize to Hudhud with various excuses and leave the ranks. Through this, Attar emphasizes that the tariqah is a difficult stage, although many people enter this path, but not all of them deserve the honor of being steadfast and courageous travelers of this path.

Fariduddin Attar's views on the universe and man.

In Attar's works, the concept of this universe is almost always visible. However, these words alone cannot be used to assess Attar's views on the world. In Attar's opinion, this world, that is, the material world, is transitory, and that world, that is, the spiritual world, is eternal. Because the spiritual world is the source and treasure of the divine being. The material world is the shell or guardian of the spiritual world. Material existence is image, spiritual existence is meaning. However, the material being is not the only existing being, but a spiritual being, a reflection of the divine being. Just as the existence of a picture is a property of meaning, so the world of things is a reflection of the divine world. The material world is a small world, that is, a small world, and the spiritual world is a big world, that is, the world of infinity. The material world has a profound harmony as the divine art of the divine. That is,

although they are different things in appearance, they are intrinsically connected with each other. Because there is a glimmer of the divine in all beings. Therefore, Attar writes:

The world that exists with his breed has such a strong connection, that everything from the fish in the water to the moon in the sky is directly related to each other. Therefore, there is an organic balance between the earth and the sky, the sea and the land, the universe and man, which consists of the power of the divine being. Because of this power, the universe is always moving, developing, changing and renewing itself. In Attar's view, total development, change and renewal are direct manifestations of the divine power. Because the world is a mirror for God. That's why Attar writes: - All objects - particles of the world are its mirror. Whatever you see, consider it as pages from his book of verses. Therefore, since the universe is a mirror, all beings in it are "pages from the book of verses" of God. I think it is possible to feel two different layers of content from Attar's relationship between the world and the mirror:

1. *The universe is a mirror. God reflects himself through this mirror. Therefore, Attar first proves that the divine being is an absolute existence through the relation of reflection in the mirror.*

2. *Therefore, the universe is not only the art of the divine being, but also the primary condition that manifests the existence of the divine being.*

Attar explains this point more clearly in the epic "Mantiq-ut-Tair" through a symbolic story. According to Attar, he was an incomparable king in beauty, "the beauty and delicacy of the universe was like a page from its secrets, and its elegance was like a verse from its face." The name of this king will spread throughout the world and everyone will be fascinated by his glory. But because the king's face is as bright as the sun, no one dares to look at him. In Attar's words, people "*couldn't bear not to see him, but they couldn't bear to see him either.*" Therefore, the king made a big mirror and looked into it. His face is reflected in the mirror, and the light from it spreads around. Through this light, people will enjoy the glory of the king. Attar summed up the story and wrote the following: - O man, your king is also a castle of the crescent moon, and the castle is brighter than the sunlight. Know your king in your heart, and thus see the throne in the flesh. Every picture, every dress that has appeared in the wilderness of this vast world is a shadow of a beautiful semurg. But, although you can't imagine it, the shadow is not an exception. Soya and Semurg are confidants and mahrams, they look forward to, look for, condition each other. If you know, your task is to get out of the shadows and strive for success. If you reach semurg, you will see the sun in the veil, then the shadow and semurg will merge, and you will see yourself in the sun. Based on Attar's idea, the unity of the world consists of the soul, and the phenomena of existence are the reflection of the soul. Therefore, in order to understand the universe, it is necessary to understand the soul. The soul is the same divine power, it is the only key that opens the secret of the universe, the essence of existence is to seek and find this key.

The goal of the conflict between transience and eternity is more eternity. The shadow still merges with the light. The basis of the universe is only one, and it is the absolute spirit. Absolute existence is again a quality or shadow of this absolute soul. Therefore, the world is considered a symbol of materiality in terms of appearance, and divinity in terms of essence. Therefore, the divine entity, that is, God, does not exist apart from the universe, but exists in unity with the universe, it is eternal and infinite. When Attar put forward this idea in his work "Ilohinama", he wrote:

- All events, objects, abundance and scarcity, negativity and positivity, denials and confirmations in the world serve to prove its existence. If you look closely, the positive qualities that exist are his. The body (materiality) of the whole being is the shadow of its greatness, a sign of its power, creativity and art. Attar's worldview becomes clearer here. He sees the whole world as pure, a proof of the divine being, and understands the material existence not only as attributes of the divine being, but as himself. He sees the glimmer of the divine in every existence. In his eyes, the ore of the universe is a bunch of shining light, wherever that light falls, the place shines. It is as if the whole universe is illuminated by the shine of a single sun.

According to Attar, the universe is a unique, unique, infinite being. He is the creation of the eternal and eternal God, who is constantly moving. Attar's vision of the world goes deep with his vision of man. In Attar's view, similar to all Sufism teachers, although man is a part of the material world in terms of external form, there is a divine light in his heart. The human body consists of different shells or skins. It is noble because its essence is spirit. With this meaning in mind, Attar exclaims to a person: - Do not forget that your jewel, that is, your soul, is the shrine of angels. On your head is the crown of caliphate. You are a child of Adam, that is, you are God's vicegerent on earth. You have fallen from heaven, you are that flower again, that is, strive towards heaven... do not stray from the qualities of humanity and divinity, your satin robe is the quality of humanity.

The material quality of man is a veil that separates him from the soul of the Absolute. It is because of this veil that a person becomes careless, repents, becomes weak at the beginning of Hijran, feels his meaningless path is dark, and his destiny is bleak. Various worries and sufferings do not give him rest. In despair, he feels that he is far from light and reality. These are expressions of the conflict between matter and spirit in the human feeling, in which if a person can subjugate his material faults, that is, tear the veil and step into the destination of spirituality, he will undoubtedly be on the throne of glory. can wear the crown. Attar wishes for Man to reach this stage and believes that he can reach it. From this, he writes sharply: - You have a treasure inside you - the secret of the absolute soul, but there is no one to guide you. In the end, what you have lost is yourself, you have become trapped in these apparent secrets. You have the essence and qualities of the creator, but you are far from his deity. Your jewel is better than all others, this jewel is the guide that will lead you to the real world. Life, the sky and the stars are your eyes, you are inside your house and in your mind you are standing on the surface of the door, you are both visible and absent.

These words of Attar are full of deep philosophical meaning and observations. Man has "the secret of the absolute soul." This is beyond any doubt for Attar. However, a person, that is, you, "is inside the house and in your mind you are standing on the surface of the door." Then what should be done to "open the door" and enter the house? There is only one answer, the door of the heart must be opened. On the same point, Attar says: "The soul is the inner world of a person, so a person must travel within. There is only one way to do this, that is to know oneself, to return to the original "I". The tragedy of man is that he is far from his essence. This can be seen from the following views of Attar: - Because you have lost yourself, you are alienated from your origin, and you are lost. You are in love with yourself, return to yourself, do not wander in the desert, return to your homeland. Faith is pure from this love of country, because your beloved is inside your pure soul. People see themselves in the image of others, but they do not know themselves. The same is true of divine acquaintance. Everyone

should first seek God within himself, and should not forget the hadith that says, "He who knows himself knows his Lord." Knowing one's self is enlightenment, and the path to enlightenment is sincerity and the opening of the heart's eyes.

In "Ilohiinama", Attar cites as an example an impressive, fiery and wonderful story about a woman who reached the throne of the kingdom by her devotion and purity. At almost every step, the woman is subjected to the suffering of lust and anger. People who fail to achieve their goals oppress women through all kinds of bad and corrupt means. But a woman puts her chastity first even in the face of death. As a result, he finally reaches his goal. In the story, Attar says the following through the language of the character: - True, no creature in the world is free from lust, a person who does not know this secret is physically disabled and defective. Such a person is not healthy. However, if the lust exceeds the limit, it will lead to anger and impurity, and then it cannot be stopped. As lust grows, love grows. However, the essence of man is love. However, love must also be limited, if it goes beyond the limit, the soul becomes weak and insignificant in the eyes of love.

Attar considers lust in moderation towards a person as an expression of health. Because he said again in the story: "If men and women do not join, how will the human race continue? Is the structure and law of the universe not broken? Because this is an orderly arrangement of divine wisdom, property, country, and world affairs are built on this basis. All living things join together, multiply and continue their offspring. This is where continuous development comes from. Humanity has undergone many mathematical developments over thousands of years and has become what it is today. Attar emphasizes that the essence of man is love, that love is the structure of the universe, the basis of the gradual development of humanity. However, if love exceeds the limit, it becomes a slave to lust, it affects purity, and it is recommended not to understand love as just lust.

As a conclusion, it should be noted that Farididdin Attar appreciates human love and praises courage in the way of human love. Because he considers human love to be "an arrangement of divine wisdom." Singing of human kindness, compassion and dignity is a characteristic of Attar and is one of the important ideological contents of his works. He illuminates this point vividly and impressively through various details - stories in his works.

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Sardorbek O‘razboy tabib o‘g‘li Sharifzoda GENDER YONDASHUV ASOSIDA O‘QUVCHI-QIZLARDA IJTIMOIIY-MADANIY KOMPITENTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI.

